

GRATITUDE AND WELL-BEING GROW TOGETHER: A STUDY OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS IN BALOCHISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigated impact of Gratitude on Psychological Well-Being. In the quest of flourishing life, understanding mutual link of these two constructs of positive psychology through empirical inquiry is crucial. This cross-sectional survey was part of the MPhil research work and correlational research design was used. Data were collected from 130 university male and female teachers through convenient sampling technique from three universities in Quetta, Balochistan. The self-report scales of (a.) Gratitude Resentment and Appreciation Test–Short Form (GRAT-SF) and (b) Psychological Well-being Scale were used. Results revealed gratitude as significant determinant of psychological well-being accounting for 14% of the variance in psychological well-being scores. Significant gender differences were also observed as female teachers reported higher levels of both gratitude and psychological well-being compared to male teachers. These findings are discussed in the context of the objectives of the present study and existent empirical literature. The findings of the present study suggest that gratitude contributes meaningfully to psychological well-being and underscores the potential value of implementing gratitude-based interventions in educational settings, particularly in under-resourced regions like Balochistan.

Keywords: Psychological Well-being, Gratitude, positive Psychology, University Teachers, Balochistan.

INTRODUCTION

Psychological Well-being is the overall mental and emotional engagement of an individual and it constitutes components such as self-acceptance, personal growth, autonomy, purpose in life, environmental mastery and positive relationships (Ryff et al., 2010). It is not only the lack of bad feelings but also the capacity to balance the good and bad experiences like grief, failure and remain functional and fulfilled in the daily life routine (Ryff & Singer, 2002). A psychologically healthy person has an appreciation for his potential ability, maintains great relationships, and actively pursues meaningful goals (Ozen, 2005; Ryff & Keyes, 2000). In this context, gratitude plays a key function as a contributing factor to psychological well-being. Gratitude is defined as the

acknowledgement of beneficial contributions from others (Garg, 2022), and it involves both emotional and cognitive elements (Zhang et al., 2022). Practices such as recalling pleasant events or expressing thanks diverts attention from negative aspects of life to positive aspects of life thus enhancing emotional stability and resilience (Watkins et al., 2003). Studies have repeatedly reported link of gratitude to increased life satisfaction and reduced levels of psychological distress (Pasha-Zaidi et al., 2021), indicating its significance in reaching and sustaining psychological well-being. As a meta-strategy, gratitude develops acceptance and improves general psychological wellbeing (Manalo et al., 2024).

Literature Review

There is an increasing body of work exploring correlation between gratitude and psychological well-being in different populations and settings. In an Indonesian study, Srivastava, S. and Vandana, (2024) observed that gratitude was significantly and positively correlated with psychological well-being among college student. A study surveyed Muslim women, observed that gratitude directly and indirectly (through meaning in life) predicted higher psychological well-being (Wahyuni, 2024). A study in Manila found a moderate positive link between gratitude and psychological well-being in secondary students (Manalo et al., 2024). However, Saeed and Mahmood (2024) observed that gratitude was positively linked to well-being among Pakistani university students during COVID-19. In Karachi, Qadr et al., (2024) found a positive correlation between gratitude and psychological well-being among undergraduate, suggesting that while gratitude relates to better well-being. A quasi-experimental study by Ahmed and Masoom (2021) showed that a three-week gratitude meditation program significantly increased both gratitude and subjective well-being among high school students. In Malaysia, Bilong et al. (2021) found a positive correlation between gratitude and psychological well-being among undergraduates. Similarly, Khodabakhsh and Ooi (2023), conducted research in Iran and found strong positive correlation between gratitude and Psychological well-being among university students during the COVID-19 pandemic. Hemarajareswari and Gupta (2021) reported strong link between gratitude and psychological well-being among college students in India. Anggraini and Palupi (2020) observed a moderate positive link between gratitude and psychological well-being among Indonesians survivors of the Lapindo mudflow disaster, demonstrating the adaptive function of gratitude amid trauma and adversity. A meta-analysis of 25 trials found that gratitude interventions, including writing letters and reflecting on thankful thoughts, significantly improved psychological well-being (Kirca et al., 2023). In the Philippines, a study examining gender and educational strands found that higher gratitude levels were associated with better psychological well-being (Maghsoudi et al., 2018). Gratitude-based therapies such as writing thank-you letters

or counting daily blessings have also been demonstrated to promote contentment and pleasure, hence boosting psychological wellness (Frontiers in Psychology, 2021; MDPI, 2023). Gender differences in psychological well-being and gratitude have also been documented across several studies. For example, Kashdan et al. (2009) found this among American college students and older adults. A study with Spanish adolescents, reported that girls reacted more favorably to gratitude interventions than boys, displaying greater usage of appreciation language and higher emotional arousal (Bono et al., 2023). A meta-analysis by Froh et al. (2023), that although both sexes benefit from thankfulness practices, females consistently demonstrated higher frequency and intensity of appreciation. Martinez and Rivera (2022), in a study from Mexico, observed that females showed bigger gains in psychological well-being after gratitude programs compared to males. In Poland, Skalski and Pochwatko (2020) reported identified that women scored higher on gratitude scales, suggesting they are more likely to detect and express appreciation as a sign of positive feeling. They also stressed that female qualities, rather than biological sex, were more strongly connected with greater well-being via appreciation expression. Finally, Yue et al. (2017), reviewing data from Chinese university students, revealed that women consistently reported considerably higher levels of thankfulness relative to men across all survey waves.

Significance of the study

While the above studies underline the widespread benefits of gratitude across all groups, there remains a noticeable gap in the literature concerning university teachers in less developed and resource-constrained places, such as Quetta, Balochistan. Though gratitude has been examined among college students and general populations in Pakistan (e.g., Hemarajareswari & Gupta, 2021; Bilong et al., 2021), university teachers in Balochistan remain underrepresented in empirical research. This population requires specific attention due to their distinct contextual challenges. Balochistan is often recognized as the least developed province in Pakistan (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2017), and its citizens notably educators endure chronic stressors such as poor infrastructure, restricted access to

educational resources, and low socio-economic status. These unfavorable situations have been associated to heightened rates of psychological distress, including anxiety and depression (WHO, 2021). In such a setting, positive psychological constructs like thankfulness may function as protective factors for general psychological well-being (Fredrickson, 2004; Emmons & Mishra, 2011). Therefore, examining the relationship between Gratitude and psychological well-being among university teachers in Quetta is not only timely but essential to filling a critical research gap and contributing to applied psychological knowledge in marginalized contexts.

Objectives of the study

1. To explore relationship of gratitude with components of psychological well-being
2. To examine the impact of gratitude on psychological well-being
3. To study gender differences on gratitude and psychological well-being

Hypotheses of the study

- H1. Greater level of gratitude is linked with greater level of psychological well-being among University Teachers.
- H2. There would be significant gender differences on gratitude and psychological well-being among University Teachers.

Method

This is a cross-sectional study with correlational research design. It aimed to examine gratitude as predictor of psychological well-being. Exploring differences in gratitude and psychological well-being between male and females was also focus of the study. A sample of 130 participants was chosen from Quetta city using convenience sampling for the study. The participants were selected from various universities in Quetta city.

Assessment Scales

The following questionnaires were used in the study.

Table 1: Demographics description of participants (N=130)

Variables	Categories	f	%
Gender	Male	54	41.5%
	Female	76	58.5%
Age	24-32	79	60.8%
	33-40	32	24.6%

Gratitude: The Gratitude Resentment and Appreciation Scale - Short Form (GRAT-SF) is a 16-item questionnaire that assesses overall Gratitude using a 9-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 9 = strongly agree). It examines lack sense of abundance, simple appreciation, and appreciation from others. Five items (3, 6, 10, 11, and 15) are reverse scored. Higher overall scores imply a more thankful view, whereas lower scores signal less frequent experiences of gratitude (Watkins et al., 2003). In the present study, the scale indicated a reliability of $\alpha = .80$

Psychological Well-being: The Psychological Wellbeing Scale is an 18-item questionnaire that examines six essential dimensions of wellbeing: Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance. Each item is graded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly agree, 7 = strongly disagree), with several items reverse scored to ensure accuracy. Higher subscale scores indicate greater psychological wellbeing (Ryff et al., 2010). In the present investigation, the scale indicated a reliability of $\alpha = .82$

Ethical Consideration

This study was conducted following the APA ethical standards such as informed consent were filled by the participants of the study prior data collection. Similarly, they were briefed that there will be no risk or harm and the data will be confidential and will be used for study purpose. This study was carried out with the approval of the Board of Advanced Studies in Research at the University of Balochistan in Quetta, which is the part of M.Phil. thesis.

Results of the study

The data were analyzed through IBM SPSS version 23 and the data were screened for normal distribution, missing values and extreme values.

	41-55	19	14.6%
University Name	SBK	59	45.4%
	UOB	38	29.2%
	Buitems	33	25.4%
Education	Graduation	66	50.8%
	Post-graduation	46	35.4%
	PhD	18	13.8%

Note: f = Frequency, % = Percentage

There were 130 participants in the sample. The majority of participants (60.8%) were in the 24- to 32-year-old age range, followed by the 33- to 40-year-old (24.6%) and the 41- to 55-year-old (14.6%). The gender distribution was 58.5% female and 41.5% male. Of the participants,

45.4% were from SBK, 29.2% were from UOB, and 25.4% were from Buitems. In terms of educational qualification, 13.8% had a PhD, 35.4% had post-graduate degrees, and 50.8% had graduated.

Table 2: Descriptive /Psychometric Properties and Correlation Coefficient for Gratitude Scale and Psychological Well-being Scale (N=130)

Scales	No of Items	M	SD	α	Range		Skew(.212)	r
					Potential Min-Mix	Actual Min-Max		
Gratitude	16	94.75	17.66	.80	9-144	56 - 129	-.32	.38**
PWB	18	73.47	15.98	.82	18-126	27 - 111	-.38	-

Note: **p < .001, PWB= Psychological Well-being, M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, α = Cronbach's alpha, r = Correlation

The descriptive and psychometric properties of the Gratitude Scale and Psychological Well-being Scale and the as well as their correlation, are shown in Table 2. The 16-item Gratitude Scale has a reliability value (Cronbach's) of .80, suggesting strong internal consistency, and a mean score of 94.75 (SD = 17.66). The actual scores in this sample vary from 56 to 129, whereas the possible score range for the Gratitude scale is 9 to 144. The skewness value is -0.32 and the

standard error is (.212). The 18-item Psychological Well-being scale has a mean score of 73.47 (SD = 15.98) and a Cronbach's α of .82, all of which indicate high reliability. Actual scores varied from 27 to 111, while its potential score range is 18 to 126. The skewness value is -0.38 and the standard error is (.212). The results indicate Gratitude has a significant strong positive correlation with Psychological Well-being (r = 0.38, p < 0.01).

Table 3: Regression Coefficient of Gratitude and Psychological Well-being (N=130)

Variable	Psychological Well-being			CI 95%				
	B	SE	β	R ²	F(1,128)	sig	LL	UL
Constant	41.33	1.45				.000	27.19	55.47
Gratitude	.34**	.07	.38	.14	20.92	.000	.19	.49

Note; **p < .001. Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-being.

Table 3 shows the effect of gratitude on psychological well-being. The R² value of .14 indicates that the predictor variable explained 14% of the variance in the outcome variable, with

F (1, 128) = 20.92, at p < .001. The results show that gratitude positively predicted psychological well-being (β = .38, p < .001).

Table 4: Difference between Male and Female on Gratitude and Psychological Well-being(N=130)

Variables	Male (n= 54)		Female (n=76)		t (128)	p	Cohen's d	95% C	
	M	SD	M	SD				LL	UL
Gratitude	87.23	19.08	100.02	14.49	-4.15	.001	-0.77	-18.91	-6.67
PWB	62.06	15.05	81.57	10.92	-8.13	.001	1.53	-24.2	-14.74

Note; **p < .001, PWB = Psychological Well-being.

Table 4 compares the gratitude scale and psychological wellbeing scores of males (n = 54) and females (n = 76). Gratitude was higher among females (M = 100.02, SD = 14.49) than among men (M = 87.23, SD = 19.08); the effect size was medium-to-large (Cohen's d = -0.77), and $t(128) = -4.15$, $p = .001$. Similarly, women's psychological well-being scores were significantly higher (M = 81.57, SD = 10.92) than men's (M = 62.06, SD = 15.05), with effect size (Cohen's d = 1.53) and $t(128) = -8.13$, $p < .001$. These findings indicate that females shows higher levels of gratitude and psychological well-being than males.

Discussion

The current study aimed to investigate the relationship between gratitude and psychological well-being among university teachers in Quetta, Balochistan, in addition to examining gender differences in these variables. The findings provided valuable information about the positive association between gratitude and psychological well-being and notable significant gender differences between the sample. Consistent with the first hypothesis (H1), the outcomes demonstrated that there was high positive correlation between gratitude and psychological well-being ($r = .38$, $p < .01$). This result justifies confirmation of the H1 and conforms to empirical studies (e.g, Watkins et al., 2003; Ryff et al., 2010; Wilson, 2016; Zainoodin et al., 2021). More recent studies have also reported similar findings. For instance, Zheng et al., (2024) found that gratitude significantly impacts the psychological well-being among Chinese teachers. Another study has revealed that adolescents with higher gratitude levels reported improved well-being (Liu et al., 2024). Issom and Nadia (2021), in their study, found that gratitude positively correlated with well-being in inclusive elementary school teachers in Jakarta, with higher gratitude levels indicating better well-being. The study shows a positive correlation between university educators' gratitude practices and improved

psychological well-being, including enhanced autonomy, personal development, and a sense of purpose, similar to (Faizal et al.,2025). Gratitude significantly predicts and accounts for 14% of the variance in Psychological Well-being, according to the results. Other recent studies such as study by Nicuță et al. (2022) have reported that gratitude interventions among university staff improved Psychological Well-being by fostering positive coping mechanisms and reducing burnout symptoms. These findings emphasize the role of Gratitude as a psychological resource that can contribute to emotional resilience, life satisfaction, and overall mental health quality in academic professionals.

Regarding the second objective, the study found that Psychological Well-being and Gratitude differed significantly by gender. The female participants had significantly higher scores in Gratitude and Psychological Well-being in comparison to male sample. These differences were statistically significant with large and medium effect sizes, suggesting that the female teachers at universities are more likely to express and feel appreciation as well as report higher Psychological Well-being. Hence, H2 is also accepted. These results are consistent with prior studies that have reported gender-based differences in well-being (e.g., Wood et al., 2010) and replicates more recent studies like that by Zhou et al. (2022), who has reported that women tend to experience and express Gratitude more frequently, and linked with greater levels of Psychological Well-being across various cultures. It may be that women are more attuned to social and emotional experiences that foster Gratitude, which in turn enhances their Psychological Well-being. A study by Garg et al. (2022) found that female teachers reported greater emotional expressivity and social connectedness, which were associated with enhanced Gratitude and mental health outcomes. In addition, cultural and social norms and beliefs could also play a role in even more emotional expression and relationship orientation of females, which would further add

to such disparities. These gender disparities may be influenced by socio-cultural factors and gender role expectations, as suggested by Rose and Rudolph (2006) and Khalid (2023) who argued that females are generally socialized to prioritize interpersonal relationships and emotional processing, thus fostering Gratitude and Psychological Well-being.

Conclusion

In the end of this study, it is concluded that gratitude is a powerful psychological strength that significantly improves mental health. Practicing gratitude promotes happier feelings and better stress management, making it a valuable tool for teachers facing daily challenges. The findings underscore the importance of gratitude in improving mental health in educational settings.

Limitations

The study had the limitations of including relatively small sample size, convenience sampling method, cross-sectional design along with self-reported data. Future studies may adopt longitudinal design to see time related effects, or qualitative interviews may be conducted with participants which may help in more diverse insight into the association between psychological strength of gratitude and psychological well-being.

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